

FRIEDEL AND CRAFTS ACETYLATION OF METHYL β -RESORCYLATE AND FRIES MIGRATION OF METHYL 2-HYDROXY-4-ACETOXYBENZOATE IN PRESENCE OF BORON TRIFLUORIDE

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Equimolecular proportions of methyl β -resorcyate and acetic anhydride have been condensed in presence of boron trifluoride etherate (2 mols.) to yield β - and γ -isomers of the products, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetyl- and -3-acetylbenzoate respectively. Fries migration of methyl 2-hydroxy-4-acetoxybenzoate in presence of (1) boron trifluoride etherate and (2) $AlCl_3$ afforded β - and γ -isomers, yields in both the cases being almost the same as in the case of the acetylations.

In an earlier paper (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 245) it was reported that in the Friedel and Crafts $\frac{1}{2}$ acetylation of methyl β -resorcyate in presence of aluminium chloride, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate was formed in considerable quantity along with 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoate. The same acetylation has been attempted in presence of boron trifluoride etherate.*

Considerable work has been carried out on the Friedel and Crafts alkylation in the presence of boron trifluoride, but only a few instances are known of acylation in its presence. Anisole (Meerwein, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 411; Meerwein and Vossen, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1934, 141, 149), phenol ("Newer Methods of Preparative Organic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1948, p. 281), resorcinol (Killeler and Lindwal, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 428) etc. have been acetylated and the corresponding ketones obtained.

In the present work equimolecular proportions of methyl β -resorcyate and acetic anhydride (1 mol.) have been condensed in presence of boron trifluoride etherate (2 mols.) by heating on a steam-bath for 2 hours, affording in good yield both the β - and γ -isomers, viz., methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetyl- and -3-acetylbenzoate respectively. Use of 3 mols. of boron trifluoride etherate did not increase the yield of either the β - or the γ -isomer. The yields are almost the same as those obtained in the case of aluminium chloride. Acetyl chloride was substituted in place of acetic anhydride and the reaction was carried out at room temperature and at 120°; under the former condition the reaction proceeded to a very limited extent and the yield was very poor. The yields of the β - and γ -isomers in case of the acetylation at 120° were almost the same as those in the case of acetic anhydride.

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In view of the interesting results obtained in the Friedel and Crafts acetylation it was also thought of interest to study the Fries migration of methyl 2-hydroxy-4-acetoxybenzoate in presence of boron trifluoride etherate (2 mols.) and aluminium chloride (2 mols.) in nitrobenzene. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. The yields of the β - and γ -isomers in both the cases were almost the same as those obtained in the Friedel and Crafts acetylation.

Though the use of boron trifluoride in place of aluminium chloride in the above reactions does not improve the yields, the reaction proceeds smoothly and the reaction mixture gives clean products.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetylation of Methyl β -Resorcyate in presence of Boron Trifluoride.—Boron trifluoride etherate (14.4 g., 2 mols.) was added to a mixture of anhydrous methyl β -resorcyate (8.4 g., 1 mol.) and acetic anhydride (5 g., 1 mol.). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 2 hours, poured in cold water while hot and subjected to steam distillation, when a white product distilled over with steam. It was collected and dried. The dried product (3 g., m. range 60°-90°) was thoroughly powdered and shaken with cold petroleum ether (b. p. 40°-60°, 30 c.c.) and filtered. The insoluble portion was crystallised from alcohol in stout needles, m.p. 122-23°, yield 1.6 g. Mixed melting point with methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoate, prepared by using aluminium chloride (*loc. cit.*), was not depressed.

The product obtained on removal of petroleum ether was crystallised from alcohol in long wooly needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 83-84°. Mixed melting point with methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate, prepared by using aluminium chloride (*loc. cit.*), was not depressed.

Methyl 2-Hydroxy-4-acetoxybenzoate.—A mixture of methyl β -resorcyate (16.8 g.), acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and sodium acetate (5 g.) was heated on a steam-bath for 5 hours. It was then poured on crushed ice when a pasty product was obtained. After filtering and washing with ice-cold water it was treated with ice-cold sodium hydroxide solution (2%) and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with cold hydrochloric acid gave a pasty mass which after drying was crystallised from alcohol (by keeping the saturated solution overnight in a refrigerator) in long needles (8 g.), m.p. 53-55°. (Found: C, 57.2; H, 4.5. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$: C, 57.1; H, 4.7 per cent). It gave wine-red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Fries Migration of Methyl 2-Hydroxy-4-acetoxybenzoate in presence of (i) Boron Trifluoride Etherate and (ii) Aluminium Chloride.—(i) Boron trifluoride etherate (14.4 g., 2 mols.) was added to methyl 2-hydroxy-4-acetoxybenzoate (10 g., 1 mol.) and heated on a steam-bath for 2 hours under reflux. The reaction mixture after pouring in cold water was subjected to steam distillation when a white product with a melting range 60°-90° distilled. It was worked up as before with petroleum ether (40°-60°). The yields of the β - and γ -isomers were 1.4 g. (m.p. 122-23°) and 0.55 g. (m.p. 83-84°) respectively.

(ii) A solution of methyl 2-hydroxy-4-acetoxybenzoate (10 g., 1 mol.) in dry nitrobenzene (20 c.c.) was added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (13.4 g., 2 mols.) in nitrobenzene (50 c.c.). The reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 160°-170° for 3 hours. After cooling ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid was added and the reaction mixture subjected to steam distillation. After the nitrobenzene had distilled over completely, the distillation was continued further when a white product with melting range 60°-90° steam distilled. It was collected and worked up with petroleum ether (40°-60°) as before. The yields of the β - and the γ -isomers were 1.4 g. (m.p. 122-33°) and 0.6 g. (m.p. 83-84°) respectively.

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